

Semantic Artefact Documentation for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library Datasets and Data Catalog

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1. Introduction and context

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library¹ is a FAIR data service designed as a digital support tool for heritage research specialists working with spectroscopic techniques. Managed by the National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics – INOE 2000, the database hosts a diverse collection of reference spectral data that can be reused across various research disciplines.

Scope of the service: The INFRA-ART Spectral Library serves as a comprehensive, dynamic database tailored for specialists working with (portable) non- or minimally invasive spectroscopic techniques such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, or Raman spectroscopy, among others. With over 2,000 curated spectra, the database allows users to analyze and compare the spectral signatures of a wide range of reference materials, facilitating the identification of unknown samples. The INFRA-ART database aims to be a FAIR and TRUST resource for researchers, fostering confidence in the quality and integrity of the data provided. The database is carefully assembled, curated, and maintained by application experts to ensure the highest standards of data quality.

The present documentation describes the semantic artefacts (Schema.org + DCAT JSON-LD schemas) developed under the FAIRMap4ART project², funded through the RDA TIGER Cascade Grants 2025³ Call. The FAIRMap4ART project was designed to address the lack of semantic interoperability of the existing datasets within the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. It builds directly on the priorities outlined in the INFRA-ART Interoperability Roadmap⁴, developed earlier in 2025 under the FAIR-IMPACT support action⁵ “*Creating EOSC-Compliant Interoperability Policies Based on the EOSC Interoperability Framework*”⁶ (February–April 2025). The core objective of the FAIRMap4ART project was to enhance object-level machine-actionability and discoverability by describing each spectral dataset in a structured, machine-readable format that enables automated access, interpretation, and reuse. The project’s objectives aligned with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)⁷, contributing to wider efforts in metadata harmonization, ontology mapping, and FAIR data stewardship. The project was also explicitly designed to implement RDA Working Group recommendations, with particular emphasis on: *Guidance on Data Granularity*⁸, and *Guidelines for Publishing Structured Metadata on the Web*⁹.

2. Objective of the present documentation

This documentation has been prepared to formally describe and preserve the semantic artefacts developed under the FAIRMap4ART project. It outlines the conceptual framework, design methodology, implementation approach, and alignment with FAIR and interoperability principles as defined by the EOSC IF and relevant RDA Working Group recommendations. It also serves as an openly licensed reference resource, supporting the reuse and adaptation of the INFRA-ART semantic artefacts

¹ <https://infraart.inoe.ro/>

² RDA Europe project ref: 2025-RDA-CG-06; project implementation: 2 June 2025 – 31 October 2025;

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/rda-tiger-cascade-grants-2025/>

⁴ Cortea, I.M. (2025). Interoperability Policy Roadmap for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15681804>

⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/creating-eosc-compliant-interoperability-policies>

⁶ Cortea, I.M. (2025). Developing an interoperability policy roadmap for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library at the National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15784837>

⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office, 2021. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

⁸ Jenkins, R., et al. (2025). Guidance on Data Granularity: Report of the RDA Data Granularity WG (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00126>

⁹ Wu, M., et al. (2021). Guidelines for publishing structured metadata on the web (3.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00066>

by other research infrastructures and heritage data services. It aims to foster wider adoption of standardized, ontology-linked metadata practices that enhance metadata richness, interoperability, and semantic transparency across the cultural heritage and scientific data communities.

Another key aim of this documentation is to gather community feedback¹⁰ and foster collaboration around the development of the INFRA-ART semantic artefacts. The INFRA-ART team invites users to review, test, and comment on the schemas, contributing to their ongoing refinement and practical validation. This open, iterative process is designed to ensure the continued relevance, sustainability, and alignment of the artefacts with evolving FAIR principles and interoperability standards.

3. Methodological framework

Interoperability aspects: Interoperability is a cornerstone of the FAIR data principles and a key requirement for sustainable, cross-domain data exchange. According to the European Interoperability Framework (EIF), interoperability is the “ability of organizations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organizations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems”¹¹. The EOSC IF is inspired by earlier work done for the EIF, and is structured according to the four interoperability layers¹² - technical, semantic, organizational and legal. Semantic interoperability ensures that both the format and meaning of data are accurately preserved and correctly interpreted during exchanges between systems or parties—in other words, “what is sent is what is understood”.

The methodological approach adopted in the FAIRMap4ART project was designed to translate the priorities of the INFRA-ART Interoperability Roadmap, with a particular focus on addressing the existing semantic interoperability gaps. It combined metadata harmonization, ontology alignment, and schema implementation activities to establish a consistent level of semantic interoperability across all currently available datasets in the INFRA-ART Spectral Library.

The development of the semantic artefacts followed a structured, five-stage workflow, summarized in the subsections below.

3.1. Metadata gap analysis

The process began with an assessment of the existing metadata structure within the INFRA-ART repository, identifying missing or unstructured descriptors that limited interoperability and machine-actionability. This analysis revealed that metadata richness and semantic precision were insufficient for dataset-level harvesting and automated discovery.

Key gaps identified in relation to semantic interoperability

Metadata area	Current status	Identified gaps
Machine-readable metadata	Basic DCAT metadata implemented on the repository landing page; provides minimal machine-readable descriptors at the top level only	No structured metadata at dataset level (e.g. JSON-LD, schema.org); no object-level descriptions
Semantic mappings	No alignment of internal metadata fields with external standards or domain ontologies	No mappings to community ontologies (e.g., CHMO, CIDOC-CRM, IUPAC)

¹⁰ Community feedback is warmly encouraged. Users and stakeholders are invited to share comments, suggestions, or improvement proposals related to the semantic artefacts. Please contact the INFRA-ART team at infraart@inoe.ro, using the subject line “feedback on semantic artefacts.”

¹¹ EIF European interoperability framework - Introduction. Available at <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/nifo-national-interoperability-framework-observatory/1-introduction> (last accessed: 2 Apr 2025)

¹² IOPEU Monitoring glossary - <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/iopeu-monitoring/glossary> (last accessed: 23 Apr 2025)

Metadata richness	Dataset metadata is limited, mostly expressed as free-text; lacks field depth and semantic typing	Metadata fields focused on human-readable descriptors, lack of granularity or formal semantics
Harvestability	Metadata is not exposed via APIs or harvesting protocols; only accessible through the repository interface	No REST APIs or OAI-PMH endpoints; metadata not indexed by OpenAIRE or aggregators
FAIRness transparency	FAIR level score of 46% according to F-UJI; with stronger performance in Accessibility, and lower scores in Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability	Moderate FAIR score limits trust and reuse; absence of transparency into machine-actionability

3.2. Metadata crosswalk and standard alignment

Internal INFRA-ART metadata fields were systematically mapped against the EOSC Pilot EDM1 metadata set¹³, the Schema.org vocabulary, and the DCAT standard. This crosswalk ensured that all dataset descriptors could be represented using widely recognized web and research data standards, supporting both human and machine readability.

3.3. Ontology and vocabulary mapping

Controlled vocabularies and domain ontologies were integrated to provide semantic depth and precision. Core ontologies included the Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO) for analytical techniques, the Ontology of Units of Measure (OM) for physical quantities and units, and the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) for heritage materials and domain concepts. Supplementary ontologies such as FIX, NCIT, MeSH, EDAM, and the W3C Time Ontology were also applied where relevant.

3.4. Schema implementation and encoding

The harmonized metadata were encoded using JSON-LD to enable embedding directly within the INFRA-ARTs landing page. Each schema combines Schema.org and DCAT elements, allowing seamless interoperability with both web-based and EOSC-aligned infrastructures. The top-level DataCatalog schema aggregates individual dataset schemas (FTIR, Raman, XRF, SWIR) via the *schema:dataset* and *dcat:Dataset* properties. Persistent identifiers—DOI, ORCID, and ROR—were included to ensure traceability and long-term reusability.

3.5. Validation and FAIRness assessment

The resulting schemas were validated using automated tools, such as F-UJI, to evaluate their compliance with FAIR principles and interoperability standards. This iterative testing process guided refinements to property mappings, ontology links, and identifier management, leading to measurable improvements in the FAIRness of the INFRA-ART metadata.

4. Overview of the semantic artefacts

A series of semantic artefacts have been developed to describe the datasets and data catalog of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library¹⁴ in a structured, machine-actionable, and interoperable way. Each artefact is implemented in JSON-LD, combining Schema.org and DCAT elements to ensure alignment with both web-discoverable metadata frameworks and EOSC-compliant research data standards. The artefacts were designed to represent the full hierarchy of the INFRA-ART repository: from the Data Catalog level, which aggregates all dataset collections, down to the dataset-level schemas describing each spectral data type. Together, these artefacts provide a coherent and extensible metadata model supporting automated harvesting, semantic linking, and reuse.

¹³ <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>

¹⁴ Detailed descriptions of the INFRA-ART datasets — including data types, data collection, and data curation practices— are available [online](#) and in related publications (see: I.M. Cortea (2024) Towards FAIR data management in heritage science research: updates and progress on the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, in *Heritage*, 7(5), 2569-2585; <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage7050123>)

Each schema has been validated for internal consistency and interoperability, ensuring harmonized metadata across dataset types and compatibility with common discovery and harvesting mechanisms. All artefacts implement dual alignment between Schema.org and DCAT elements, allowing metadata to be simultaneously exposed for web indexing (Schema.org) and for structured harvesting through DCAT/RDF. Persistent identifiers¹⁵— ORCID for creators, and ROR for institutions and funders—are embedded throughout to ensure traceability, provenance, and reuse.

Together, these artefacts constitute the semantic backbone of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, ensuring that its spectral datasets are not only accessible and reusable but also machine-interpretable and interoperable within the broader open-science ecosystem.

INFRA-ART semantic artefacts overview

Artefact type	Scope/Description	Standard alignment	File	Description in landing page source code
DataCatalog Schema	Describes the complete INFRA-ART Spectral Library, aggregating all dataset collections (FTIR, Raman, XRF, SWIR) and linking them via <i>schema:dataset</i> and <i>dcat:Dataset</i> properties. Includes catalog-level metadata such as title, description, creator, publisher, keywords, and funding information.	Schema.org + DCAT	JSON-LD	<i>RDA Dual Schema – Full Catalogue, Version 1 (August 2025)</i>
FTIR Dataset Schema	Describes the ATR-FTIR spectral dataset collection, including measurement techniques, variables measured, file data structure, as well as information on the creator, publisher, keywords, access conditions, etc.	Schema.org + DCAT	JSON-LD	<i>RDA Dual Schema – FTIR Dataset Collection, Version 1 (August 2025)</i>
XRF Dataset Schema	Describes the XRF spectral dataset collection, including measurement techniques, variables measured, file data structure, as well as information on the creator, publisher, keywords, access conditions, etc.	Schema.org + DCAT	JSON-LD	<i>RDA Dual Schema – XRF Dataset Collection, Version 1 (August 2025)</i>
Raman Dataset Schema	Describes the Raman spectral dataset collection, including measurement techniques, variables measured, file data structure, as well as information on the creator, publisher, keywords, access conditions, etc.	Schema.org + DCAT	JSON-LD	<i>RDA Dual Schema – Raman Dataset Collection, Version 1 (August 2025)</i>
SWIR Dataset Schema	Describes the SWIR spectral dataset collection, including measurement techniques, variables measured, file data structure, as well as information on the creator, publisher, keywords, access conditions, etc.	Schema.org + DCAT	JSON-LD	<i>RDA Dual Schema – SWIR Dataset Collection, Version 1 (August 2025)</i>

5. Ontology and vocabulary mappings

The semantic artefacts describing the INFRA-ART Spectral Library datasets and data catalog incorporate controlled vocabularies and domain ontologies to enhance metadata precision, semantic clarity, and sustainable interoperability across systems. Ontology alignment was performed to harmonize dataset descriptors with well-established community vocabularies and ontologies, facilitating machine-readable semantics and consistent terminology across datasets.

¹⁵ Persistent identifiers (DOIs) for the dataset collections will be assigned following their formal deposition on Zenodo in 2026. In the current release of the schemas, each dataset collection is referenced through stable URI-based identifiers within the INFRA-ART repository.

The selection of ontologies followed three key criteria:

- Relevance to spectroscopy and materials science (for describing analytical techniques, measurements, and substances/materials);
- Adoption and persistence within established research data infrastructures (to ensure long-term stability and interoperability); and
- Coverage and compatibility with Schema.org and DCAT properties, allowing seamless integration into web and EOSC-aligned metadata ecosystems.

The ontologies and vocabularies applied in the current version of the schemas are summarized below.

Ontologies and controlled vocabularies applied in the INFRA-ART schemas

Vocabulary / Ontology	Namespace prefix	Scope and use
Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO)	chmo	Describes general spectroscopy terms (e.g., FTIR spectrum, Raman spectrum, reflectance spectrum, spectroscopy)
Ontology of Units of Measure (OM)	om	Provides standardized representations for measurement units and physical quantities (e.g., wavenumber, nanometre, micrometre, millisecond, milliwatt)
Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)	aat	Supplies terminology for materials (e.g., pigments, artists' materials), techniques, and heritage object types
BioAssay Ontology (BAO)	bao	Provides terminology for selected technical concepts not covered by CHMO or AAT (e.g. definition of transmittance as a measured variable)
nmrCV	nmr	Provides terminology for selected technical concepts not covered by CHMO or AAT (e.g. data processing annotation baseline corrected)
National Cancer Institute Thesaurus (NCIT)	ncit	Provides terminology for selected chemical and physical concepts not covered by CHMO or AAT such as processing status (raw, converted to reflectance), variable units (e.g., pixel), x-ray acquisition parameters
Functional Imaging Ontology (FIX)	fix	Provides terminology for selected technical concepts not covered by CHMO or AAT (e.g. measurement techniques, X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy)
Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)	mesh	Provides terminology for selected technical concepts not covered by CHMO or AAT (e.g. Hyperspectral imaging measurement technique)
EDAM Ontology	edam	Applied for general data and format terms to enhance compatibility with FAIRsharing. File formats (e.g., CSV)
IANA Media Types	—	MIME type for CSV (text/csv)
W3C Time Ontology	time	Used for temporal descriptions such as acquisition or creation dates of the datasets (start and end years)
Persistent Identifiers	ORCID, ROR	Unambiguous references to dataset creators and organizations

Notes: Certain ontologies (e.g., NCIT, FIX, MeSH) originate from life or medical sciences and were adopted provisionally due to the lack of specialized alternatives for heritage and conservation datasets. Future updates will aim to align these terms with domain-specific ontologies emerging from heritage science initiatives.

6. Implementation details

All semantic artefacts developed for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library are implemented as embedded JSON-LD blocks within the INFRA-ART home page source code. This approach enables the entire metadata structure—covering both the data catalog and the individual dataset collections (FTIR, Raman, XRF, SWIR)—to be centrally exposed and harvested from a single source.

The JSON-LD encoding ensures that metadata are both human-readable and machine-actionable, supporting discovery by search engines, harvesting by repositories, and integration within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem.

The implementation follows a dual-encoding strategy, combining classes and properties from both Schema.org and DCAT/DCTERMS. The catalog is typed as both *DataCatalog* and *dcat:Catalog*, while each collection (e.g. FTIR) is typed as both *Dataset* and *dcat:Dataset*. Key elements such as titles, descriptions, licenses, dates, and subjects are expressed using both Schema.org properties (e.g. *name*, *description*, *license*) and their DCAT/DCT equivalents (e.g. *dct:title*, *dct:description*, *dct:license*). This approach ensures interoperability across web-based metadata systems and research-data infrastructures, allowing the same artefacts to be recognized by both general search platforms (e.g. Google Dataset Search) and specialized aggregators (e.g. EOSC Portal, OpenAIRE).

6.1 Structural overview

The DataCatalog schema acts as the top-level artefact, describing the overall INFRA-ART Spectral Library and linking the individual dataset schemas—FTIR, Raman, XRF, and SWIR—through the *dataset* and *dcat:dataset* properties. Each dataset is identified by a stable URI corresponding to its specific query within the repository and inherits core descriptive elements from both Schema.org and DCAT.

The schemas incorporate ontology-linked metadata describing:

- **Measurement techniques and instrumentation** (e.g. ATR-FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, XRF, SWIR reflectance), expressed via *measurementTechnique* and linked to CHMO, FIX, and related ontologies;
- **Variables measured and measurement units**, represented through *variableMeasured* as *PropertyValue* entries aligned with OM, BAO, and NCIT (e.g. Wavenumber, Transmittance);
- **Material type and object category**, captured using *keywords* as *DefinedTerm* objects referencing Getty AAT and CHMO terms (e.g. pigments, artists' materials, paint types);
- **Creators, publishers, and contributing organizations**, represented as *Person* and *Organization* entities with ORCID and ROR identifiers, also cross-referenced through *dct:creator* and *dct:publisher*;
- **Temporal coverage**, defined using the W3C Time Ontology (*time:Interval*, *time:Instant*) and DCAT/DCTERMS temporal elements (*dct:temporal*, *dcat:startDate*, *dcat:endDate*);
- **Keywords, license, and access information**, aligned with both Schema.org and DCAT best practices.

In addition, the JSON-LD blocks embedded in the landing page include detailed technical and structural metadata, using the *additionalProperty* mechanism to describe:

- **Data structure** (e.g. CSV layout, axes, column indices, and value ranges);
- **Acquisition conditions** (e.g. ATR mode, resolution, number of scans, spectral range);
- **Processing status** (e.g. baseline correction);
- **Collection size and file format**, with references to EDAM and IANA MIME types;
- A *dcat:distribution* block specifying the *dcat:accessURL*, *dct:format*, and *dcat:mediaType* for CSV distributions.

6.2 Persistent identifiers and referencing

To ensure traceability, attribution, and long-term reusability, each schema integrates persistent identifiers (PIDs):

- **ORCID** for individual contributors, ensuring unambiguous identification of creators and authors;
- **ROR** for organizational affiliations and funders, referenced through *identifier*, *dct:publisher*, and *dct:spatial*;

- **URI-based identifiers** for the catalog and dataset collections, corresponding to stable URLs within the INFRA-ART repository.

Notes: In the current release of the semantic artefacts (Version 1, August 2025), each dataset collection is referenced through stable URI-based identifiers within the INFRA-ART repository. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned following the formal deposition of the dataset collections on Zenodo in 2026.

The schemas also include a **citation block** (*citation* as *ScholarlyArticle*), referencing the primary INFRA-ART publication, ensuring clear scholarly attribution.

6.3 Validation and quality assurance

All JSON-LD artefacts were validated using automated tools, including Google’s Dataset Validator (for Schema.org syntax and structured-data compliance), F-UJI, and FAIRCORE4EOSC CAT (for FAIRness and interoperability assessment). The validation workflow focused on:

- Ensuring correct JSON-LD serialization and namespace definitions for Schema.org, DCAT, and ontology prefixes;
- Confirming that all mandatory metadata elements identified in the EDM1–Schema.org/DCAT crosswalk were correctly implemented, including titles, identifiers, descriptions, licensing, creators, and dataset landing page URLs, etc;
- Verifying the use of persistent identifiers (ORCID, ROR) and resolvable ontology URIs (CHMO, AAT, OM, EDAM, etc.);
- Assessing metadata completeness and improvements in FAIRness metrics (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability).

7. FAIRness and interoperability assessment

The semantic artefacts were evaluated to confirm their alignment with the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and the EOSC IF. The assessment focused on both the technical implementation of the JSON-LD schemas and their semantic consistency with established metadata standards and domain ontologies. FAIRness evaluation conducted using the F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool¹⁶ demonstrated substantial improvement across all aspects of metadata quality. The overall FAIR score increased from 46%¹⁷ to 92%, with Interoperability scoring 6 out of 6 metrics — reflecting the successful implementation of structured metadata and integration with community vocabularies. The complete F-UJI report is available at the following link: <https://www.f-uji.net/view/4442#>.

7.1 Key findings

The assessment revealed measurable progress across all four FAIR dimensions:

- **Findability** — All datasets are now described with machine-actionable metadata and stable URI-based identifiers, ensuring discoverability through search engines and EOSC-aligned catalogs. Dual Schema.org/DCAT encoding supports cross-platform harvesting and indexing.
- **Accessibility** — Access conditions are clearly defined through Schema.org and DCAT properties (*conditionsOfAccess*, *dct:accessRights*), while contact and creator information are consistently linked via ORCID and ROR identifiers.
- **Interoperability** — Metadata elements are fully aligned with the EOSC Pilot-EDM1 metadata set, and ontology terms (CHMO, AAT, OM, FIX, EDAM, etc.) are consistently linked through

¹⁶ Devaraju, A., and Huber, R. (2025). F-UJI – An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool (v3.5.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118508>

¹⁷ FAIR score before the implementation of the FAIRMap4ART project, based on the F-UJI assessment conducted in May 2025

persistent URIs. The interoperability score confirms that all metadata fields are semantically enriched and machine-actionable.

- **Reusability** — Each dataset schema includes a clear license (CC BY-NC 4.0), structured citation information for the INFRA-ART publication, and detailed contextual metadata describing measurement techniques, variables, acquisition parameters, and data structure.

7.2 Impact and future integration

The implementation of structured semantic artefacts has substantially increased the machine-actionability and interoperability of INFRA-ART metadata, enabling: integration with EOSC-aligned services such as OpenAIRE; greater visibility through Google Dataset Search and other Schema.org-compliant aggregators; and, easier reuse and cross-linking with external heritage-science and spectroscopy data resources.

Future work will focus on:

- Assigning DOIs to all dataset collections via Zenodo in 2026;
- Periodic revalidation of FAIRness using updated tools and indicators;
- Continued ontology enrichment to capture new analytical methods and material domains;
- Incorporating community feedback to maintain long-term alignment with evolving FAIR and EOSC standards.

8. Reuse guidelines

The semantic artefacts and accompanying documentation developed for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library are openly released under a Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal license¹⁸. This ensures that the artefacts can be freely reused, modified, and redistributed without restriction, supporting broad adoption across research and heritage data communities. These resources are intended to assist researchers, data curators, repository managers, and digital heritage professionals in implementing FAIR and interoperable metadata practices. By providing ready-to-use examples of Schema.org/DCAT-aligned JSON-LD structures and ontology mappings, the work carried out under the FAIRMap4ART project aims to accelerate the adoption of semantic interoperability across related infrastructures and repositories.

The JSON-LD schemas and ontology mappings can be directly reused or adapted by other repositories and data services seeking to:

- Implement Schema.org/DCAT-compliant metadata for dataset or catalog descriptions;
- Integrate FAIR-aligned ontology references (e.g., CHMO, OM, AAT) into their own metadata;
- Establish dual-level catalog and dataset descriptions compatible with EOSC and web discovery;
- Extend existing metadata crosswalks to cover spectroscopy or other analytical datasets;

9. Dissemination and community engagement

The documentation and semantic artefacts developed for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library are shared openly through the INFRA-ART website and the Zenodo record accompanying this publication. All artefacts and documentation will be maintained as part of the INFRA-ART data service, with revised versions released following the addition of new datasets or the refinement of metadata schemas. Versioning information is included in each JSON-LD block (via the *version* and *dct:hasVersion* properties).

¹⁸ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>

The JSON-LD schemas are embedded directly in the source code of the INFRA-ART website landing page¹⁹—identified as *RDA dual schemas*—providing a single, machine-actionable metadata entry point for all dataset collections that users can easily browse and explore. The INFRA-ART team actively encourages community review and feedback to improve the artefacts’ quality and applicability across domains. Users are invited to share comments, suggestions, or improvement proposals by contacting infraart@inoe.ro (subject: *feedback on semantic artefacts*).

This documentation is a living resource, and will be periodically reviewed to reflect progress, incorporate community input, and align with evolving interoperability standards and best practices. In the long term, the maintenance of the semantic artefacts will remain a core component of the INFRA-ART data service interoperability strategy, ensuring their continued accessibility, relevance, and integration within the broader FAIR and EOSC ecosystem.

10. Annexes

Annex A: Crosswalks between EDMII recommended metadata properties, Schema.org, and DCAT

Annex B: Mapping of EDMII properties to INFRA-ART datasets descriptors

Annex C: Crosswalk overview of the controlled vocabularies used across the dataset schemas

¹⁹ [view-source:https://infraart.inoe.ro/](https://infraart.inoe.ro/)

Annex A.

Crosswalks between EDM I recommended metadata properties²⁰, Schema.org, and DCAT

EDMI property	Level *	Description	Schema.org equivalent	DCAT equivalent	Notes
name	M	A descriptive name for the dataset	name	dct:title	Human-readable title of the dataset
description	M	A short summary describing a dataset	description	dct:description	Short text or abstract
identifier	M	The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of dataset	identifier	dct:identifier	Prefer persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI)
url	M	The location of a page describing the dataset	url	dcat:landingPage	Human-readable landing page
creator	M	The creator/author of this dataset	creator / author	dct:creator	Person or organization
dateCreated	M	The date on which the dataset was created	dateCreated	dct:issued	Use ISO 8601 format
license	M	A license under which the dataset is distributed	license	dct:license	Use persistent license URLs (e.g., CC BY 4.0)
dataStandard	M	The standard in which the content of the dataset is represented	conformsTo	dct:conformsTo	Link to the metadata/content standard
dateModified	M	The date on which the dataset was most recently modified	dateModified	dct:modified	Last update timestamp in ISO 8601 format
accessUrl	M	The link to download the dataset	contentUrl	dcat:accessURL	Direct link to file or API endpoint
accessInterface	M	The type of interface to present the dataset	(custom property)	dcat:accessService	May require extension or description in notes
structure	R	The description of the structure of the dataset	(custom or distribution detail)	(no direct match)	Could use dcat:mediaType + free text
includedIn	R	A dataset or data catalog which contains the dataset	isPartOf	dct:isPartOf	Used for parent datasets or catalogs
measurementTechnique	R	A technique or technology used in a dataset corresponding to the method used for measuring the corresponding variables	measurementTechnique	(no direct match)	Extend with domain ontologies (e.g., CHMO)
keywords	R	Keywords or tags used to describe the dataset	keywords	dcat:keyword	List or semicolon-separated string
variablesMeasured	R	The variables that are measured in the dataset	variableMeasured	(no direct DCAT match)	Can be modeled with external vocabularies or qb:measureType

²⁰ <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties>

format	R	The format in which the content of the dataset is encoded to present the information, typically a MIME format	encodingFormat	dct:format	Use standard MIME types (e.g., text/csv)
scientificType	R	Scientific domain or type of the information provided in the dataset	about	dcat:theme / dct:subject	Use controlled vocabularies (e.g., Fields of Science)
includes	R	A dataset or data catalog contained in the dataset	hasPart	dct:hasPart	Inverse of includedIn
contentType	R	Type of content provided in the dataset based on its origin and type of processes (raw, processed, summarised)	additionalType	dct:type	Raw, processed, summarized — define vocabulary
size	R	Size of the dataset using a digital information multiple unit byte symbol (MB, GB, PT, ...)	contentSize	dcat:byteSize	Use digital size values with unit
authentications	R	Type of authentication required to access the dataset	(no Schema.org match)	dct:accessRights	Indicate open/restricted/embargoed
version	O	The version of the dataset	version	owl:versionInfo	Semantic versioning if possible
metric	O	Metric to provide some quantitative or qualitative information about the dataset	(custom)	(custom)	Could describe citations, downloads, etc.
sameAs	O	Other URLs that can be used to access the dataset page	sameAs	owl:sameAs	Use for canonical vs alternate references
spatialCoverage	O	The location depicted or described in the content	spatialCoverage	dct:spatial	Can use GeoNames, ISO country codes, etc.
temporalCoverage	O	The property indicates the period that the content applies to	temporalCoverage	dct:temporal	Use date ranges, formatted ISO 8601
citation	O	A citation or reference to another work that describes the dataset	citation	dct:bibliographicCitation	Could point to papers, datasets, etc.
referenceCitation	O	A citation or reference to that describes the dataset	(custom)	(custom)	Could use same as citation or specialized property
compression	O	Type of compression used in the dataset	compression	(custom)	Could describe .zip, .gz, etc.
authorisations	O	Type of authorisation required to access the dataset	(no Schema.org match)	dct:accessRights	Extend description of access policies

Requirement levels: M – minimum, R – Recommended, O – Optional

Annex B.

Mapping of EDM properties to INFRA-ART datasets descriptors

EDMI property	Description	INFRA-ART dataset descriptor	Action required
name	A descriptive name for the dataset	"INFRA-ART FTIR Spectral Data Collection" "INFRA-ART XRF Spectral Data Collection" "INFRA-ART Raman Spectral Data Collection" "INFRA-ART SWIR Spectral Data Collection"	None
description	Short summary describing the dataset	Define for each set of data type (e.g. "Collection of curated ATR-FTIR spectra of art-related materials relevant to heritage and conservation science, part of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library.")	None
identifier	Persistent identifier for the dataset	Not available yet	Assign Zenodo DOI upon publication next year
url	Landing page describing the dataset	Not available yet	Provide Zenodo landing page URL upon publication
creator	Creator/author of the dataset	ATR-FTIR: Ioana Cortea; XRF: Ioana Cortea; Raman: Luminita Ghervase; SWIR: Lucian Ratoiu	None
dateCreated	Date dataset was created	First datasets online in 2021	None
license	Dataset license	CC BY-NC 4.0	None
dataStandard	Standard used to represent dataset content	Metadata schemas: DCAT, Schema.org	Implement dataset-level JSON-LD/DCAT markup
dateModified	Date of last modification	Last update date available on landing page	Automate update tracking at dataset level
accessUrl	Download link for dataset	Not available yet	Provide Zenodo download link upon publication
accessInterface	Interface to present dataset	Web interface	Implement API endpoints for harvesting
structure	Description of dataset structure	CSV with header (key-value metadata) + tabular data; Define for each set of data type.	Include schema documentation in repository
includedIn	Dataset/catalog containing this dataset	INFRA-ART Spectral Library	None
measurementTechnique	Measurement method/technology	ATR-FTIR, XRF, Raman spectroscopy, Hyperspectral imaging	None
keywords	Keywords or tags	Define for each set of data type FTIR: "FTIR spectroscopy", "FTIR spectrum", "ATR-FTIR", "Pigments", "Artists' materials"; XRF: "XRF spectroscopy", "XRF spectrum", "XRF", "Pigments", "Artists' materials"; Raman: "Raman spectroscopy", "Raman spectrum", "Pigments", "Artists' materials"; SWIR: "Reflectance spectrum", "Pigments", "Artists' materials";	Link to controlled vocabularies
variablesMeasured	Variables measured in dataset	Define for each set of data type:	Link to ontology terms for variables

		FTIR: Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹), Transmittance (%); XRF: Energy (keV), Intensity (counts/s); Raman: Wavenumber/Raman shift (cm ⁻¹), Raman intensity (a.u.); SWIR: Wavelength (nm), Reflectance (%);	
format	Data encoding format	CSV	None
scientificType	Scientific domain/type	Spectroscopy	Link to domain ontology term
includes	Dataset/catalog contained within this dataset	Links to full FTIR, XRF, Raman, SWIR datasets	Review linking approach
contentType	Content type (raw, processed)	ATR-FTIR: processed; XRF: raw; Raman: raw; SWIR: processed	None
size	Dataset size	Not available yet	Include size after Zenodo deposit
authentications	Authentication required	None	None
version	Dataset version	Version 1	Update for new releases
metric	Quantitative/qualitative dataset metric	FTIR: 971 (spectra); XRF: 1039; Raman: 129; SWIR: 50;	Automate counting on update
sameAs	Alternative URLs for dataset page	Not available yet	Add Zenodo DOI and other persistent links
spatialCoverage	Geographic location of dataset content	INCD INOE 2000, Măgurele, Romania	None
temporalCoverage	Time period dataset applies to	2020–2025	None
citation	Citation describing the dataset	I.M. Cornea et al. (2023). <i>INFRA-ART: An Open Access Spectral Library...</i> , ACM J. Computing and Cultural Heritage, 16(2):40. https://doi.org/10.1145/3593427	None
referenceCitation	Additional reference describing dataset	–	Not applicable
compression	Compression used	Currently none	Package as ZIP for Zenodo
authorisations	Authorisation required	Available upon File Access Request	Remove restriction at Zenodo publication

with green – descriptors implemented in the current schemas; with red – descriptors left out in this phase; to be added after the datasets are published in Zenodo next year.

Annex C.

Crosswalk overview of the controlled vocabularies used across the dataset schemas

Concepts and techniques			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
Spectroscopy	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000228	"about"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300179535	
Spectrum	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000800	"keywords"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300056171	
FTIR spectrum	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000853	"keywords"
ATR-FTIR	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000763	"keywords" + "measurementTechnique"
FTIR spectroscopy	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000636	"keywords"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379403	
Raman spectrum	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000823	"keywords"
Raman spectroscopy	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000656	"keywords" + "measurementTechnique"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300266192	
XRF	FBbi	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FBbi_0000608	"keywords"
XRF spectroscopy	FIX	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/FIX_0000673	"keywords" + "measurementTechnique"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300224161	
Reflectance spectrum	CHMO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CHMO_0000937	"keywords"
Short-wave infrared spectroscopy	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300438632	"keywords"
Hyperspectral imaging	MeSH	http://id.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/D000081862	"keywords" + "measurementTechnique"
	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300389881	
Measurement axes / variables			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
Wavenumber	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Wavenumber	"variableMeasured"
Transmittance	BAO	http://www.bioassayontology.org/bao#BAO_0000071	"variableMeasured"
Raman shift	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Wavenumber	"variableMeasured"
Intensity (a.u.)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/one	"variableMeasured"
Energy	NCIT	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C67276	"variableMeasured"
Net count rate	NCIT	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C94878	"variableMeasured"
Wavelength	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Nanometre	"variableMeasured"

Reflectance	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Percent	"variableMeasured"
Acquisition parameters (units)			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
Resolution (cm ⁻¹)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Wavenumber	"Acquisition Conditions"
Number of scans	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Number	"Acquisition Conditions"
Spectral range (nm)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Nanometre	"Acquisition Conditions"
Integration time (ms)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Millisecond	"Acquisition Conditions"
Frame period (ms)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Millisecond	"Acquisition Conditions"
Lateral resolution (px)	NCIT	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C48367	"Acquisition Conditions"
Current intensity (µA)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/ElectricCurrent	"Acquisition Conditions"
Tube voltage (kV)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/ElectricPotential	"Acquisition Conditions"
Analysis time (s)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Time	"Acquisition Conditions"
Laser spot size (µm)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Micrometre	"Acquisition Conditions"
Laser power (mW)	OM-2	http://www.ontology-of-units-of-measure.org/resource/om-2/Milliwatt	"Acquisition Conditions"
Processing status of the data			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
Raw (unprocessed)	NCIT	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/NCIT_C142663	"Processing status"
Baseline corrected	nmrCV	http://nmrML.org/nmrCV#NMR:1400074	"Processing status"
File format / media type			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
SV (format)	EDAM	http://edamontology.org/format_3752	Structure (file format)"
text/csv (media type)	IANA	https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/text/csv	Structure (file format)"
Domain keywords (in term of data applications)			
Concept / Label	Voc/ Ont	Term (IRI)	Used in (Schema.org)
Heritage Science	Getty AAT	https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300417282	"keywords"
Conservation science	Getty AAT	https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379510	"keywords"
Pigments	Getty AAT	https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013109	"keywords"
Artists' materials	Getty AAT	https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300014842	"keywords"
Inorganic pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013111	"keywords"
Synthetic inorganic pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013113	"keywords"
Natural organic pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013121	"keywords"
Organic pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013120	"keywords"
Mineral pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300375550	"keywords"
Plant pigment	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300013123	"keywords"

Organic material	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300011792	"keywords"
Organic material	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300014254	"keywords"
Oil (organic material)	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300014254	"keywords"
Resin (organic material)	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300012882	"keywords"
Gouache (paint)	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300070114	"keywords"
Watercolor (paint)	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300070114	"keywords"
Oil paint	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300015050	"keywords"
Casein paint	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300015033	"keywords"
Tempera	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300015062	"keywords"
Spray paint	Getty AAT	http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300391376	"keywords"